

WINDING PATTERN DETERMINATION FOR PRESSURE VESSELS COMPRISING FIBRE BUNDLES OF FINITE DIMENSIONS

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Abstract

The most important steps in the design procedure of a composite pressure vessel are the shape determination and the derivation of suitable winding patterns. Both can be expressed in terms of the required amount of wound circuits. This paper presents a methodology for matching the number of circuits dictated by strength calculations to those dictated by winding patterns. The main key for this matching procedure can be found in terms of the main characteristic fibre properties: cross sectional dimensions and tensile strength. The fibre trajectories here are geodesic, and they are not subjected to any additional turning around at the poles of the treated vessel. In this sense, the solution may be regarded as optimal since it guarantees minimal fibre length, minimal fibre stacking, minimal number of required circuits, minimal fibre overlap and maximal occupation of the fibre bundle strength.

Keywords: filament winding, isotenoid, winding pattern, Diophantine

Introduction

The increasing popularity of filament wound objects has resulted in their introduction as mass products. As a consequence of this development, the demands on such products are not only limited to their performance, but also include cost and production technology related aspects.

This multidisciplinary collection of requirements has raised the demands on their design procedure. Focussing on composite pressure vessels, the usual design strategy is a sequential one: selection of the fibre bundles, shape determination, winding pattern derivation and production time minimisation (usually obtained by optimisation techniques).

In the specialised fields of shape determination, pattern derivation and production process optimisation, a significant number of useful papers can be found. However, when focussing on the interaction between the implemented design parameters and their influence on the final product geometry, one may conclude that this has probably been underestimated. A common illustration of this is the trial to minimise the production time of a particular wound vessel, while the required number of circuits (dictated from the strength calculations) does not match the necessary number to obtain a suitable pattern. The result of this shortcoming is additional wound fibre length, excessive fibre stacking at the polar areas of the vessel, increased production time, and larger deviations from the original isotenoidal geometry. The latter generally results in a weaker construction.

This paper attempts to fill the gap between “design for strength” and “design for producibility”. The main idea is to match the results from the strength calculations to the optimal conditions for minimal production time, minimal fibre stacking and minimal deviations from the original geometry. In order to achieve this, the shape-determining parameters are indirectly introduced as variables in the so-called Diophantine equations, which lead to suitable winding patterns. The main objective of the method presented here is to match the strength-dictated number of wound circuits to the solution of the Diophantine equations by varying the fibre geometry and tensile strength.

After a short description of the pressure vessel geometry, an extensive treatment of the wound fibre topology is provided. The next presented item consists of a description of the procedure for obtaining suitable winding patterns, followed by the matching criteria. In order to illustrate the methodology, a typical example is given, followed by the conclusions and recommendations.

Pressure vessel geometry

We consider here the typical isotensoidal pressure vessel geometry, calculated according to the netting theory [1,3]. The vessel is subjected to both an internal pressure P and a particular axial load A at the polar area, see figure 1:

Fig. 1. General pressure vessel geometry

The radius of the polar opening is ρ_0 and the number of fibre bundles crossing the equatorial parallel is N . The (constant) tensile force in every fibre bundle is f . We introduce the dimensionless parameters:

$$Y = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \quad Z = \frac{z}{\rho_0} \quad a = \frac{Nf}{\pi P \rho_0^2} \quad k_a = \frac{A}{\pi P \rho_0^2} \quad (1)$$

The differential equation describing the meridian profile satisfying the axial force equilibrium is [7]:

$$Z'(Y) = - \frac{k_a Y + Y^3}{\sqrt{a^2 (Y^2 - 1) - (k_a Y + Y^3)^2}} \quad (2)$$

The argument of the square root involved in equation (2) should be positive and real. The corresponding 6th degree equation has two double real roots and one double imaginary root. The positive real roots define the Y -interval $\{Y_{\min}, Y_{\max}\}$ corresponding with positive values of the square root argument. The creation of an isotensoidal pressure vessel is only possible for Y -values belonging to that interval. It is important to notice that generally the value of Y_{\min} is slightly bigger than 1. In the case of geodesic winding, the fibre can never become tangential to the pole; in other words, the polar winding angle will never reach the value of $\pi/2$ [rad] (see equation (3)).

Trajectories of zero-thickness fibre bundles

The pressure vessel is covered with geodesic fibre trajectories; the corresponding local winding angles are given by the equation of Clairaut, see figure (2):

$$\sin \alpha(Y) = \frac{1}{Y} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Geodesic fibre trajectory at a locus Y

The differential equation describing a geodesic trajectory on a shell of revolution is given by [4,5]:

$$\phi'(Y) = \frac{\sqrt{1+Z'^2(Y)} \tan \alpha(Y)}{Y} \quad (4)$$

Substitution of equations (2) and (3) into (4) leads to:

$$\phi'(Y) = \frac{a}{Y\sqrt{Y^2-1}} \sqrt{\frac{Y^2-1}{a^2(Y^2-1)-(k_a Y+Y^3)^2}} \quad (5)$$

We introduce:

$$q = \left(\frac{Y_{\max}}{Y_{\min}}\right)^2 \quad r = \frac{k_a}{Y_{\max}^2} \quad Y^2 = Y_{\max}^2 \cos^2 \theta + Y_{\min}^2 \sin^2 \theta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (6)$$

After substitution of definitions (6) into (5), the final expression for the geodesic fibre trajectory becomes:

$$\phi'(Y) = \frac{\sqrt{q(1+q+2qr)}}{(q \cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta) \sqrt{2+q+2qr+(q-1) \cos^2 \theta}} \quad (7)$$

Integration yields:

$$\phi(\theta) = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1+q+2qr}{q[1+2q(1+r)]}} \Pi\left(\frac{q-1}{q}; \theta \middle| \frac{q-1}{[1+2q(1+r)]}\right) \quad (8)$$

where $\Pi(n; \theta | m)$ stands for an incomplete elliptic integral of the third kind [8]. Note that when proceeding from the polar opening Y_{\min} to the equator Y_{\max} , the corresponding elliptical θ -coordinate proceeds from $\theta = \pi/2$ to $\theta = 0$. When completing one wound circuit, the total angular propagation ϕ_e becomes:

$$\phi_e = 4\phi(0) \quad (9)$$

The vessel is symmetric with respect to its equatorial plane; we consider here a fibre trajectory from the pole to the equator. The angular difference between two neighbouring circuits depends exclusively on $\phi(Y=Y_{\min}) - \phi(Y=Y_{\max}) = \Phi$. To describe this angular propagation, we introduce:

$$K_g = \frac{\pi}{2} - \Phi \quad (10)$$

The angular difference between two adjacent circuits is:

$$\Delta K_g = 2\pi - 4\Phi = 4K_g \quad (11)$$

Note that in the case of creating isotensoidal pressure vessels, the absolute value of Φ is always smaller than $\pi/2$.

Trajectories of real fibre bundles

We consider here the polar area of an isotensoidal pressure vessel (figure (3)). The applied fibre bundle is geometrically characterised by a width b and a thickness δ . Occasionally, depending on the final construction of the end caps, the fibre bundle may not be placed tangentially to the polar opening (ρ_0), but slightly further away. This distance is denoted by ϵ .

Fig. 3. Fibre geometry at the pole

The meridional length differential is given by:

$$dS(Y) = \sqrt{1 + Z'^2(Y)} dY \quad (12)$$

This differential can not be determined for values below Y_{\min} . However, in reality, the vessel liner continues until $Y=1$. For this very small region we assume that the meridian profile is horizontal (in practice, this region is limited to a few micrometers). The dimensionless Y -location ν of the fibre centreline should satisfy the following condition:

$$(Y_{\min} - 1) + \int_{Y_{\min}}^{\nu} S'(Y) dY = \frac{B}{2} + E - \Delta \frac{Z'(\nu)}{\sqrt{1 + Z'^2(\nu)}} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$B = \frac{b}{\rho_0} \quad E = \frac{\epsilon}{\rho_0} \quad \Delta = \frac{\delta}{\rho_0} \quad (14)$$

For every combination (q, r, B, E, Δ) , an unique ν -value can be obtained; $\nu = \nu(q, r, B, E, \Delta)$. Compared to the dimensionless fibre bundle, the major difference is that the wound trajectory is now tangent to the polar opening at $Y = \nu$; the corresponding winding angel is equal to $\pi/2$. These considerations lead to:

$$\sin \alpha(Y) = \frac{\nu}{Y} \quad (15)$$

One should notice that the fibre trajectories remain geodesic. The corresponding differential equation is:

$$\phi'(Y) = \frac{av}{Y\sqrt{Y^2 - v^2}} \sqrt{\frac{Y^2 - 1}{a^2(Y^2 - 1) - (k_a Y + Y^3)^2}} \quad (16)$$

Substitution of the dimensionless parameters (6) into equation (16) leads to:

$$\frac{d\phi}{d\theta} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}v \sqrt{\frac{q(1+q+2qr)\{1+q\{2r+q[r^2+q(1+r^2)]\}+c(q-1)\cos(2\theta)\}}{[3+q(3+4r)+(q-1)\cos(2\theta)][-2qv^2(1+q+2qr)+c(q+1)+c(q-1)\cos(2\theta)]}}{1+q+(q-1)\cos(2\theta)} \quad (17)$$

where:

$$c = 1 + q + 2qr + q^2(1+r)^2 \quad (18)$$

Despite the similarity of equations (5) and (16), the geodesic equation for “real” fibres is increasingly complicated. Integration of this expression can only be performed by numerical techniques. The equatorial radius Y_{\max} remains unchanged and corresponds with $\theta = 0$. When the fibre crosses the polar area, the winding angle becomes equal to $\pi/2$. This implies that the differential presented in equation (17) should reach infinity. Hence, the limiting value for θ at the pole ($= \theta_p$) should satisfy the following condition:

$$[3+q(3+4r)+(q-1)\cos(2\theta_p)][-2qv^2(1+q+2qr)+c(q+1)+c(q-1)\cos(2\theta_p)] = 0 \quad (19)$$

At an arbitrary locus θ , the geodesic ϕ -coordinate can be found by applying:

$$\phi(\theta) = \int_{\theta_p}^{\theta} \phi' dt \quad (20)$$

As introduced in the previous section, the angular propagation between two adjacent circuits is given by equations (10) and (11) where:

$$\Phi = \int_{\theta_p}^0 \phi' dt \quad (21)$$

The angular propagation parameter K_g is, for generally small fibre bundle width variation, practically linear to b , see figure 4:

Fig. 4. The angular circuit propagation parameter as a function of the applied fibre bundle width.

Winding patterns

The most important parameter for the creation of suitable winding patterns is the angular propagation between two neighbouring circuits. Since we assume that the shape is remaining unchanged during the winding process, the main parameter influencing K_g becomes the dimensionless fibre centreline position factor, ν (equation (17)). This quantity is exclusively controlled by the fibre bundle dimensions B and Δ , and the distance parameter E (see equations (13) and (14)). The basic winding pattern terminology is given below:

Fig. 5. Top view of the equatorial plane of a wound object, including the sequential circuit numbers.

In the presented figure, the black dots indicate fibre passages from the upper polar surface to the lower one; the opposite situation applies on the white dots. At the equator, the width of a particular fibre bundle becomes:

$$b_w = \frac{b}{\cos \alpha(Y_{\max})} \quad (22)$$

where $\alpha(Y_{\max})$ is obtained by equation (15). The number of b_w 's fitting into the equatorial circumference is:

$$n = \frac{2\pi Y_{\max} \rho_0}{b_w} \quad (23)$$

The angular difference between two neighbouring circuits is:

$$\Delta K_g = 4K_g \quad (24)$$

The pattern constant is:

$$p = \text{Integerpart} \left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta K_g} \right) \quad (25)$$

A winding pattern is determined by the so-called Diophantine equation of the first order [2,5,6]:

$$\begin{aligned}
(p+1)k - n &= \frac{1}{d} && \text{leading pattern} \\
pk - n &= -\frac{1}{d} && \text{lagging pattern}
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where: d = desired number of complete layers, p is given by equation (24), k = integer number, and n is given by equation (23). When a suitable combination of integers is found [4,5,6], the required angular propagation can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_g^{\text{leading}} &= \frac{1}{4} \frac{2\pi}{p+1} \left(1 + \frac{1}{nd} \right) \\
K_g^{\text{lagging}} &= \frac{1}{4} \frac{2\pi}{p} \left(1 - \frac{1}{nd} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Required number of filaments

The design of an isotensoidal pressure vessel, can be described in two parameters: $\{a, k_a\}$ (equations (1) and (2)) or $\{q, r\}$ (equation (6)). De relation between these parameters, is [7]:

$$\begin{aligned}
a &= \frac{[1+q+2qr+q^2(1+r)^2]^{3/2}}{q(1+q+2qr)} \\
r &= \frac{k_a}{Y_{\max}^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

We assume now that the design is given in terms of a and k_a and that the strength of the applied fibre bundle per unit of cross sectional area is F . Every circuit creates (per layer) two fibre bundles passing the equatorial cross section (the upgoing and undergoing winding, black and white dots in figure 5): $N = 2nd$. According to this and equations (1) and (14), we obtain:

$$\frac{f = Fb\delta}{a\pi P\rho_0^2 = 2ndF} \Rightarrow nd = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{P}{F} \frac{a}{B\Delta} \tag{29}$$

The required effective number of filaments clearly depends on a “load / strength” ratio P/F , and a dimensionless geometric parameter $a/B\Delta$.

Matching the mechanical and geometrical properties

As stated in the introduction, the main objective of the presented methodology is to provide a tool for matching the resulting pattern to the required number of windings dictated by strength calculations. Substituting equation (29) into (27) and recalling (21) results in:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{F}{P} \frac{B\Delta}{a} &= \frac{p}{2} - \frac{1+p}{\pi} \Phi && \text{Leading pattern} \\
\frac{F}{P} \frac{B\Delta}{a} &= \frac{1-p}{2} + \frac{p}{\pi} \Phi && \text{Lagging pattern}
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

where, for fixed q and r (or a and k_a) values (equations (13), (14), (17), (19), (20) and (21)):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi &= \Phi(\phi', \theta_p) \\
\phi' &= \phi'(v) \\
\theta_p &= \theta_p(v) \\
v &= v(B, E, \Delta)
\end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

The complete matching procedure can be summarised as adjusting a $\{f, B, \Delta\}$ combination (equation (30), left-hand side) to a $\{E, B, \Delta\}$ combination.

In practice, the excentricity value E is limited up to a few tenths of millimetres. In addition, the fibre strength f is usually predetermined as a typical value for e.g. glass or carbon fibres. The fibre thickness δ should be, in order to avoid excessive fibre stacking at the polar areas, as small as possible. An increased thickness value (B) is generally advantageous for limiting the required production time. However, too large values may introduce significant strength problems since the fibre topology will considerably deviate from the theoretical one; this situation may lead to the requirement to apply additional circuits on the vessel. Moreover, the available fibre spools are limited to certain width ranges. Within these ranges, an optimal solution should be found in terms of minimal strength reduction and minimal production costs, under one important constraint: equation (29) should be satisfied. If the latter can not be fulfilled, a certain fibre overlap at the equator may be acceptable.

Example

We consider here a pressure vessel with $a = 50$ and $k_a = -10$. These parameters lead to: $Y_{\min} = 1.01648$ and $Y_{\max} = 7.71872$ (positive real solution by setting the denominator of equation (2) as equal to zero). The corresponding q and r -values are respectively 57.6625 and -0.168 (equations (28)). The design pressure P is set equal to 20 [MPa] and the applicable fibre bundle width range is $\{5, 20\}$ [mm]. The radial offset ϵ at the polar area is set equal to 1 [mm]. We further assume that the available fibre spools contain fibre bundles having a thickness of 0.3 [mm] and a tensile strength within the range $\{4000, 4500\}$ [MPa].

The objectives are:

- Maximal occupation of the mechanical fibre properties
- Preferably one wound layer
- Minimal number of required circuits
- Fibre overlap at the equator: less than 1 [mm]
- Fixed fibre width
- Fixed radial offset (E)

The given width range generates a spectrum of corresponding Φ -values (equation (21)). These Φ -values lead to a collection of pattern constants p (equations (24) and (25)). In addition, a collection of corresponding n -values may be obtained by applying equations (22) and (23). The suitable patterns are (solution of equations (27) for $d = 1$ [4]):

Leading:

Pattern numbers $\{(p+1), kd, nd\}$:

$$\{\{16, 24, 383\}, \{15, 12, 179\}\}$$

K_g -values (equation(27)):

$$\left\{ \frac{12\pi}{383}, \frac{6\pi}{179} \right\}$$

$\{F, nd, \text{ fibre overlap in [mm]}\}$ (equation (29)):

$$\{(4330.9, 383, 0.0365085), (4200.98, 179, 0.432124)\}$$

Lagging:

Pattern numbers $\{p, kd, nd\}$:

$$\{(15, 21, 316), (15, 20, 301), (15, 19, 286), (15, 18, 271), (15, 17, 256), \\ (15, 16, 241), (15, 15, 226), (15, 14, 211), (15, 13, 196), (14, 12, 169), \\ (14, 11, 155), (14, 10, 141), (14, 9, 127), (13, 8, 105)\}$$

K_g -values(equation(27)):

$$\left\{ \frac{21\pi}{632}, \frac{10\pi}{301}, \frac{19\pi}{572}, \frac{9\pi}{271}, \frac{17\pi}{512}, \frac{8\pi}{241}, \frac{15\pi}{452}, \frac{7\pi}{211}, \frac{13\pi}{392}, \frac{6\pi}{169}, \frac{11\pi}{310}, \right. \\ \left. \frac{5\pi}{141}, \frac{9\pi}{254}, \frac{4\pi}{105} \right\}$$

$\{F, nd, \text{ fibre overlap in [mm]}\}$ (equation (29)):

$$\{(2566.78, 316, 4.30708), (2698.51, 301, 3.98631), (2844.5, 286, 3.63189), \\ (3007.19, 271, 3.23824), (3189.62, 256, 2.79846), (3395.61, 241, 2.30394), \\ (3630.04, 226, 1.74377), (3899.25, 211, 1.10395), (4211.58, 196, 0.366209), \\ (2974.79, 169, 5.40187), (3253.87, 155, 4.31097), (3590.72, 141, 3.00348), \\ (4005.37, 127, 1.40768), (3340.29, 105, 5.76973)\}$$

The best solution in terms of the above presented desired properties is the second leading pattern: the required ν -value to generate $K_g = 6\pi/179$ is $\nu = 1.16426$, leading to $b = 11.141$ [mm]. The required tensile strength for the fibre to be applied is equal to 4201 [MPa] while the necessary number of circuits becomes equal to 179. The result is depicted below:

Fig. 6. The resulting pattern, after completing 15 circuits

Conclusions and recommendations

In this paper, a method is presented regarding the integral design of composite pressure vessels. The main objective is to simultaneously satisfy the requirements of minimum weight and production time under the restriction of creating a suitable winding pattern with least possible fibre overlap at the equator, and without any additional correction of the turn-around value K_g . As a result of this, the number of required fibre bundles (dictated by strength calculations) corresponds exactly to the necessary number of circuits in order to create a fully geodesic winding pattern.

Among strength calculations, the simultaneous implementation of the resulting fibre path geometry and winding patterns, creates significant benefits in terms of facilitating the design procedure and obtaining an optimal product both in the sense of performance as well as production costs and quality. This facilitation is particularly achieved by avoiding the usual trial and error work as an attempt to distribute the obtained number of circuits according to some acceptable pattern. The most common result in this case is the activation of some additional turning around of the fibre trajectories at the polar areas; this inevitably results in significant fibre stacking and generally more weight of the constructed vessel.

A profitable strategy is to combine relatively broad fibre bundles with minimal thickness into a pattern requiring a minimum number of circuits. However, due to the deviations from the ideal isotensoid theory (dimensionless fibre), the tension loads in the fibres may become significantly higher. This amplification results in the need for enlarging the number of circuits, thus the total weight of the wound product. In conclusion, for a final design decision, the deviations from the ideal isotensoidal geometry should also be considered.

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